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ABSTRACT

^1H spin-lattice relaxation studies have been performed for binary systems, including glycerol as the first component and alanine, glycine, and aspartic acid (with different levels of deuteration) as the second one. The relaxation studies have been performed in the frequency range from 10 kHz to 10 MHz vs temperature. A theoretical framework, including all relevant ^1H - ^1H and ^1H - ^2H relaxation pathways, has been formulated. The theory has been exploited for a thorough interpretation of a large set of the experimental data. The importance of the ^1H - ^2H relaxation contributions has been discussed, and the possibility of revealing dynamical properties of individual liquid components in binary liquids has been carefully investigated. As far as the dynamical properties of the specific binary liquids, chosen as an example, are considered, it has been shown that in the presence of the second component (alanine, glycine, and aspartic acid), both molecular fractions undergo dynamics similar to that of glycerol in bulk.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) relaxation studies are highly appreciated as a source of information about molecular motion. In this respect, NMR relaxometry (relaxation experiments performed vs resonance frequency) is of special importance. With the fast field cycling technology, one can perform relaxation experiments in a broad frequency range, encompassing at least three orders of magnitude—from 10 kHz to 10 MHz (referring to ^1H). This implies that one can probe dynamical processes on the timescale from milliseconds to nanoseconds in a single experiment. The further unique advantage of NMR relaxometry is the possibility to reveal the mechanism of the molecular (and ionic) motion from the shape of the frequency dependence of the spin-lattice relaxation rates. According to the relaxation theory,^{1–4} the relaxation rate is given as a linear combination of spectral density functions that are Fourier transforms of the corresponding time correlation functions. The mathematical form of the correlation function (and, hence, the spectral density) depends on the mechanism of

motion. Consequently, analyzing the shape of relaxation dispersion profiles, one can unambiguously distinguish between translational and rotational dynamics. Moreover, one can identify the dimensionality of the translation dynamics, distinguishing between three-dimensional (3D) isotropic translation motion,^{5–10} two-dimensional (2D) surface diffusion,^{7,11–15} and sub-diffusive motion in confinement.^{7,16–18} In addition to this exceptional potential (one can hardly find other experimental methods that give insights into the mechanism of motion, not only its time scale), NMR relaxometry offers a straightforward way to determine the translational diffusion coefficient. Mathematical properties of the spectral density function describing 3D diffusion imply a linear dependence of the relaxation rate on the squared root of the resonance frequency. Then, from the slope of this linear dependence, one can calculate the translation diffusion coefficient.^{6,19–21} The calculated value represents the relative translation diffusion coefficients—in the case of non-correlated motion, it is given as a sum of self-diffusion coefficients of the interacting molecules (ions); otherwise, the relative diffusion coefficient is smaller than the sum

of the self-diffusion coefficients. In this way, by comparing the relative translation diffusion coefficient with the self-diffusion ones (obtained by means of NMR diffusometry), one can go even further and get experimental insights into correlation effects in molecular motion.²¹ These advantages of NMR relaxometry have been exploited for molecular and ionic liquids.^{19–26}

However, relaxation processes are a quantum-mechanical phenomenon that requires proper theoretical models in terms of the relaxation pathways and spin interactions before proceeding with the dynamical properties. This subject has been addressed for ionic liquids, as in this case, cations often include ¹H nuclei, while anions include ¹⁹F (and/or ³¹P) nuclei.^{20,21,24,27} Consequently, the relaxation scenario involves several homo-nuclear and hetero-nuclear relaxation contributions associated with the corresponding magnetic dipole–dipole interactions that can be of intra-molecular (intra-ionic) and inter-molecular (inter-ionic) origin. Although the quantum-mechanical framework of the relaxation processes for such systems is complex, one can recourse to ¹H and ¹⁹F experiments to maintain “resolution” enabling to probe dynamics of both ions. For mixtures composed of liquids, including ¹H as the only kind of NMR active nuclei, distinguishing between relaxation contributions originating from both components possess a challenge. One should not think that for such systems one observes bi-exponential relaxation processes and that the individual components stem from the different molecular fractions. First, to detect bi-exponential relaxation (assuming that theoretically the process is bi-exponential), the relaxation rates must be sufficiently different and the contributions (amplitudes) of the relaxation components must be comparable. These conditions can be fulfilled for heteronuclear systems as, then, the bi-exponentiality originates from the quantum-mechanical framework.^{1–4,28–30} For homo-nuclear systems, the overall relaxation results from a network of mutual, homo-nuclear dipole–dipole interactions and represents the averaged effect.

In this work, the subject of exploiting NMR relaxometry for binary, homo-nuclear mixtures has been addressed from the theoretical and experimental sides. As far as the theory is concerned, we provide relaxation expressions, including relaxation pathways relevant for two component systems for the following cases: both components include only ¹H nuclei: one of the components is fully deuterated and one of the components is partially deuterated. Deuteration is often exploited to maintain “resolution,” but one has to be aware that ²H nuclei also possess magnetic moments and ¹H–²H relaxation contributions cannot be always just neglected. The theoretical picture is compared with ¹H spin-lattice relaxation data for binary mixtures, including (fully protonated) glycerol as the first component and alanine, glycine, and aspartic acid (with different levels of deuteration) as the second one. This work provides a framework for exploiting NMR relaxometry for binary mixtures, pointing at the same time the limitations one encounters.

II. THEORY

¹H relaxation processes are predominantly caused by magnetic dipole–dipole interactions. The interactions may be of

intra-molecular and inter-molecular origins. Consequently, the overall ¹H spin-lattice relaxation rate, $R_1(\omega_H)$ (ω_H denotes the ¹H resonance frequency in angular frequency units), is given as a sum of inter-molecular and intra-molecular relaxation contributions, $R_{1,H}^{intra}(\omega_H)$ and $R_{1,H}^{inter}(\omega_H)$, respectively,

$$R_1(\omega_H) = R_1^{intra}(\omega_H) + R_1^{inter}(\omega_H). \quad (1)$$

The inter-molecular dipole–dipole interactions fluctuate in time mainly as a result of relative translation diffusion of the interacting species, while the intra-molecular dipole–dipole coupling is modulated by rotational and internal dynamics of the molecule. For ¹H–¹H dipole–dipole interactions, the relaxation contributions $R_1^{intra,HH}(\omega_H)$ and $R_1^{inter,HH}(\omega_H)$ are given as^{7,8,10}

$$R_1^{intra,HH}(\omega_H) = C_{intra}^{HH} [J_{intra}(\omega_H) + 4J_{intra}(2\omega_H)], \quad (2)$$

$$R_1^{inter,HH}(\omega_H) = C_{inter}^{HH} [J_{inter}(\omega_H) + 4J_{inter}(2\omega_H)]. \quad (3)$$

The dipolar relaxation constant C_{intra}^{HH} is defined as $C_{intra}^{HH} = \frac{3}{10} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{\gamma_H^2 \hbar}{r^3} \right)^2$, where r denotes an effective inter-spin distance, representing interactions between all pairs of ¹H nuclei in the molecule; γ_H is the ¹H gyromagnetic factor; and other symbols have their well-known meaning. Assuming that the correlation function characterizing the fluctuations of the intra-molecular interactions is exponential (this is the case for isotropic rotational motion), the spectral density function $J_{intra}(\omega_H)$ takes the Lorentzian form,

$$J_{intra}(\omega_H) = \frac{\tau_c}{1 + (\omega_H \tau_c)^2}, \quad (4)$$

where τ_c is referred to as a correlation time (a characteristic time constant describing the time scale of the stochastic fluctuations of the spin interactions). The dipolar relaxation constant for the inter-molecular dipole–dipole coupling is defined as $C_{inter}^{HH} = \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma_H^2 \hbar \right)^2$. For isotropic (three-dimensional) translation diffusion, the corresponding spectral density function $J_{inter}(\omega_H)$ can be expressed as^{5,6,8–10,19,20}

$$J_{inter}(\omega_H) = \frac{72}{5} \frac{1}{d^3} N_H \int_0^\infty \frac{u^2}{81 + 9u^2 - 2u^4 + u^6} \frac{u^2 \tau_{trans}}{u^4 + (\omega_H \tau_{trans})^2} du, \quad (5)$$

where N_H denotes the number of hydrogen atoms per unit volume. Equation (5) originates from the so-called force free hard sphere model that assumes that the interacting molecules are hard spheres with hydrogen atoms in their center. Consequently, according to this model, the quantity d , referred to as the distance of the closest approach, is given as a sum of the radii of the interacting molecules (that gives the molecular diameter for identical molecules). The translational correlation time, τ_{trans} , is defined as $\tau_{trans} = \frac{d^2}{D^{rel}}$, where

D_{trans}^{rel} is the relative translation diffusion coefficient; for uncorrelated motion, the relative diffusion coefficient is given as a sum of the self-diffusion coefficients of the interaction molecules, $D_{trans,1}$ and $D_{trans,2}$: $D_{trans}^{rel} = D_{trans,1} + D_{trans,2}$. For identical molecules, one gets $D_{trans}^{rel} = 2D_{trans}$, where D_{trans} denotes the self-diffusion coefficient.

This implies that for a system that is composed of one kind of molecules and when the only relevant relaxation pathway is provided by ^1H - ^1H dipole-dipole interactions, the ^1H spin-lattice relaxation rate is given as

$$R_1(\omega_H) = C_{intra}^{HH} \left[\frac{\tau_c}{1 + (\omega_H \tau_c)^2} + \frac{4\tau_c}{1 + (2\omega_H \tau_c)^2} \right] + C_{inter}^{HH} \frac{72}{5} \frac{1}{d^3} N_H \int_0^\infty \frac{u^2}{81 + 9u^2 - 2u^4 + u^6} \times \left[\frac{u^2 \tau_{trans}}{u^4 + (\omega_H \tau_{trans})^2} + \frac{4u^2 \tau_{trans}}{u^4 + (2\omega_H \tau_{trans})^2} \right] du, \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } \tau_{trans} = \frac{d^2}{2D_{trans}}.$$

When the system included two kinds of molecules, but ^1H - ^1H dipole-dipole interactions still remain the only relevant relaxation mechanism, Eq. (6) should be extended to the following form:

$$R_1(\omega_H) = C_{intra,1}^{HH} \left[\frac{\tau_{c,1}}{1 + (\omega_H \tau_{c,1})^2} + \frac{4\tau_{c,1}}{1 + (2\omega_H \tau_{c,1})^2} \right] + C_{intra,2}^{HH} \left[\frac{\tau_{c,2}}{1 + (\omega_H \tau_{c,2})^2} + \frac{4\tau_{c,2}}{1 + (2\omega_H \tau_{c,2})^2} \right] + C_{inter}^{HH} \frac{72}{5} \frac{1}{d_{1,1}^3} N_{H,1} \frac{N_{H,1}}{N_{H,1} + N_{H,2}} \int_0^\infty \frac{u^2}{81 + 9u^2 - 2u^4 + u^6} \left[\frac{u^2 \tau_{trans}^{1,1}}{u^4 + (\omega_H \tau_{trans}^{1,1})^2} + \frac{4u^2 \tau_{trans}^{1,1}}{u^4 + (2\omega_H \tau_{trans}^{1,1})^2} \right] du + C_{inter}^{HH} \frac{72}{5} \frac{1}{d_{2,2}^3} N_{H,2} \frac{N_{H,2}}{N_{H,1} + N_{H,2}} \int_0^\infty \frac{u^2}{81 + 9u^2 - 2u^4 + u^6} \left[\frac{u^2 \tau_{trans}^{2,2}}{u^4 + (\omega_H \tau_{trans}^{2,2})^2} + \frac{4u^2 \tau_{trans}^{2,2}}{u^4 + (2\omega_H \tau_{trans}^{2,2})^2} \right] du + C_{inter}^{HH} \frac{72}{5} \frac{1}{d_{1,2}^3} \frac{2N_{H,1}N_{H,2}}{N_{H,1} + N_{H,2}} \int_0^\infty \frac{u^2}{81 + 9u^2 - 2u^4 + u^6} \left[\frac{u^2 \tau_{trans}^{1,2}}{u^4 + (\omega_H \tau_{trans}^{1,2})^2} + \frac{4u^2 \tau_{trans}^{1,2}}{u^4 + (2\omega_H \tau_{trans}^{1,2})^2} \right] du. \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) includes two relaxation terms representing the intra-molecular relaxation contributions for the two molecular fractions (denoted as 1 and 2); the terms include the corresponding dipolar relaxation constants, $C_{intra,1}^{HH}$ and $C_{intra,2}^{HH}$, and the correlation times, $\tau_{c,1}$ and $\tau_{c,2}$, respectively. Following this line, Eq. (7) includes three inter-molecular relaxation contributions that correspond to ^1H - ^1H dipole-dipole interactions between molecules 1 (1-1), molecules 2 (2-2) and molecules 1 and 2 (1-2). The distances of closest approach, $d_{1,1}$, $d_{2,2}$, and $d_{1,2}$, are associated with the pairs of molecules: 1-1, 2-2, and 1-2, respectively. Analogously, the translational correlation times are defined as $\tau_{trans}^{1,1} = \frac{d_{1,1}^2}{2D_{trans,1}}$, $\tau_{trans}^{2,2} = \frac{d_{2,2}^2}{2D_{trans,2}}$, and $\tau_{trans}^{1,2} = \frac{d_{1,2}^2}{D_{trans}^{rel}}$, while $N_{H,1}$ and $N_{H,2}$ denote the number of hydrogen atoms per unit volume of the mixture, belonging to molecules 1 and molecules 2, respectively. When the same diffusion coefficients are assumed for both molecular fractions, Eq. (7) converges to

$$R_1(\omega_H) = C_{intra,1}^{HH} \left[\frac{\tau_{c,1}}{1 + (\omega_H \tau_{c,1})^2} + \frac{4\tau_{c,1}}{1 + (2\omega_H \tau_{c,1})^2} \right] + C_{intra,2}^{HH} \left[\frac{\tau_{c,2}}{1 + (\omega_H \tau_{c,2})^2} + \frac{4\tau_{c,2}}{1 + (2\omega_H \tau_{c,2})^2} \right] + C_{inter}^{HH} \frac{72}{5} \frac{1}{d^3} N_H \int_0^\infty \frac{u^2}{81 + 9u^2 - 2u^4 + u^6} \times \left[\frac{u^2 \tau_{trans}}{u^4 + (\omega_H \tau_{trans})^2} + \frac{4u^2 \tau_{trans}}{u^4 + (2\omega_H \tau_{trans})^2} \right] du, \quad (8)$$

where d denotes an effective distance of the closest approach and N_H is the total number of hydrogen atoms per unit volume of the mixture, while $\tau_{trans} = \frac{d^2}{D_{trans}^{rel}} = \frac{d^2}{2D_{trans}}$ (provided that $D_{trans}^{rel} = 2D_{trans}$).

When one of the molecular fractions is fully deuterated (let assume fraction 2), one should include into the description a relaxation term corresponding to the intermolecular ^1H - ^2H

dipole–dipole interactions. The inter-molecular ^1H – ^2H (^1H – D) relaxation contribution is given as^{2–4}

$$R_1^{inter,HD}(\omega_H) = C_{inter}^{HD} [J_{inter}(\omega_H - \omega_D) + 3J_{inter}(\omega_H) + 6J_{inter}(\omega_H + \omega_D)], \quad (9)$$

where ω_D denotes the ^2H resonance frequency (in angular frequency units); $\omega_D \cong 0.16\omega_H$. The dipolar relaxation constant, C_{inter}^{HD} , is defined as $C_{inter}^{HD} = 4\left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi}\gamma_H\gamma_D\hbar\right)^2$, where the ^2H gyromagnetic factor follows the relationship $\gamma_D \cong 0.16\gamma_H$. Consequently, the overall spin-lattice relaxation rate is given as

$$R_1(\omega_H) = C_{intra}^{HH} \left[\frac{\tau_c}{1 + (\omega_H\tau_c)^2} + \frac{4\tau_c}{1 + (2\omega_H\tau_c)^2} \right] + C_{inter}^{HH} \frac{72}{5} \frac{1}{d_{1,1}^3} N_H \int_0^\infty \frac{u^2}{81 + 9u^2 - 2u^4 + u^6} \left[\frac{u^2\tau_{trans}^{1,1}}{u^4 + (\omega_H\tau_{trans}^{1,1})^2} + \frac{4u^2\tau_{trans}^{1,1}}{u^4 + (2\omega_H\tau_{trans}^{1,1})^2} \right] du + C_{inter}^{HD} \frac{72}{5} \frac{1}{d_{1,2}^3} N_D \int_0^\infty \frac{u^2}{81 + 9u^2 - 2u^4 + u^6} \left[\frac{u^2\tau_{trans}^{1,2}}{u^4 + ((\omega_H - \omega_D)\tau_{trans}^{1,2})^2} + \frac{3u^2\tau_{trans}^{1,2}}{u^4 + (\omega_H\tau_{trans}^{1,2})^2} \frac{6u^2\tau_{trans}^{1,2}}{u^4 + ((\omega_H + \omega_D)\tau_{trans}^{1,2})^2} \right] du, \quad (10)$$

where N_H and N_D denote the numbers of ^1H and ^2H nuclei, respectively, per unit volume of the mixture. The number of variables in Eq. (10) can be reduced by assuming the same translation diffusion coefficient for both molecular fractions and using an effective distance of closest approach, d ; then, $\tau_{trans}^{1,1} = \tau_{trans}^{1,2} = \tau_{trans} = \frac{d^2}{2D_{trans}}$. In the case of partial deuteration of the molecules forming fraction 2, the relaxation rate is given as

$$R_1(\omega_H) = C_{intra}^{HH,1} \left[\frac{\tau_{c,1}}{1 + (\omega_H\tau_{c,1})^2} + \frac{4\tau_{c,1}}{1 + (2\omega_H\tau_{c,1})^2} \right] + C_{intra}^{HH,2} \left[\frac{\tau_{c,2}}{1 + (\omega_H\tau_{c,2})^2} + \frac{4\tau_{c,2}}{1 + (2\omega_H\tau_{c,2})^2} \right] + C_{intra}^{HD,2} \left[\frac{\tau_{c,2}}{1 + ((\omega_H - \omega_D)\tau_{c,2})^2} + \frac{3\tau_{c,2}}{1 + (\omega_H\tau_{c,2})^2} + \frac{6\tau_{c,2}}{1 + ((\omega_H + \omega_D)\tau_{c,2})^2} \right] + C_{inter}^{HH} \frac{72}{5} \frac{1}{d^3} N_H \int_0^\infty \frac{u^2}{81 + 9u^2 - 2u^4 + u^6} \left[\frac{u^2\tau_{trans}}{u^4 + (\omega_H\tau_{trans})^2} + \frac{4u^2\tau_{trans}}{u^4 + (2\omega_H\tau_{trans})^2} \right] du + C_{inter}^{HD} \frac{72}{5} \frac{1}{d^3} N_D \int_0^\infty \frac{u^2}{81 + 9u^2 - 2u^4 + u^6} \left[\frac{u^2\tau_{trans}}{u^4 + ((\omega_H - \omega_D)\tau_{trans})^2} + \frac{3u^2\tau_{trans}}{u^4 + (\omega_H\tau_{trans})^2} \frac{6u^2\tau_{trans}}{u^4 + ((\omega_H + \omega_D)\tau_{trans})^2} \right] du. \quad (11)$$

The second intra-molecular component is theoretically present only when the partially deuterated molecule contains at least two ^1H nuclei; however, in that case, the ^1H – ^2H intra-molecular relaxation contribution is usually negligible (or can hardly be distinguished from the ^1H – ^1H intra-molecular contribution). The dipolar relaxation constant $C_{intra}^{HD,2}$ is defined as $C_{intra}^{HD,2} = \frac{2}{5}\left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi}\gamma_H\gamma_D\hbar\right)^2$; the parameters N_H and N_D retain their meaning.

When the condition $\omega_H\tau_{trans} < 1$ is fulfilled, the spectral density $J_{inter}(\omega_H)$ [Eq. (5)] can be expanded into Taylor series, yielding $J_{inter}(\omega_H) \cong a - b\sqrt{\omega_H}$, where $a = J_{inter}(0)$ and $b = \frac{2^{3/2}\pi}{45(D_{trans}^{rel})^{3/2}} = \frac{\pi}{45D_{trans}^{3/2}}$ (assuming $D_{trans}^{rel} = 2D_{trans}$). The rotational motion is faster than the translational one—according to the Stokes–Einstein formula, the ratio between the translational and rotational correlation times for spherical molecules is 9. Consequently, in the frequency range when $\omega_H\tau_{trans} < 1$, the intra-molecular relaxation contributions are expected to be frequency independent. Consequently, a linear dependence of the overall relaxation rate $R_1(\omega_H)$ on $\sqrt{\omega_H}$

is expected in the low frequency range. When $R_1(\omega_H)$ is given by Eq. (6) or Eq. (8), the slope B of the linear dependence is given as^{8,19}

$$R_1(\omega_H) \cong R_1(0) - B\sqrt{\omega_H} = R_1(0) - N_H\pi \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi}\gamma_H^2\hbar\right)^2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{2} + 8}{15}\right) (D_{trans}^{rel})^{-3/2} \sqrt{\omega_H} = R_1(0) - N_H\pi \left(\frac{1 + 4\sqrt{2}}{30}\right) \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi}\gamma_H^2\hbar\right)^2 D_{trans}^{-3/2} \sqrt{\omega_H}. \quad (12)$$

In the last equality, $D_{trans}^{rel} = 2D_{trans}$ has been set. In the presence of ^1H – ^2H inter-molecular dipole–dipole interactions [Eqs. (10) and (11)], Eq. (12) should be extended to the following form:

$$R_1(\omega_H) \cong R_1(0) - \left[\left(\frac{\sqrt{2} + 8}{15}\right) N_H\pi \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi}\gamma_H^2\hbar\right)^2 + \frac{16\sqrt{2}}{9} N_D\pi \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi}\gamma_H\gamma_D\hbar\right)^2 \right] \sqrt{\omega_H}$$

TABLE I. Composition of mixtures; glycerol ($M = 92.09$ g/mol) was used as the first compound.

Second compound	Weight ratio: second compound/glycerol
l-aspartic acid-h ₇	1.45
l-alanine-h ₇	0.97
Glycine-h ₅	0.82
l-aspartic acid-d ₇	1.52
Glycine-d ₅	0.87
l-aspartic acid-d ₃	1.48
l-alanine-d ₃	1.00
l-alanine-d ₄	1.01

$$\left(D_{trans}^{rel}\right)^{-\frac{3}{2}}\sqrt{\omega_H} = R_1(0) - \left[\left(\frac{1+4\sqrt{2}}{30}\right)N_H\pi\left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi}\gamma_H^2\hbar\right)^2 + \frac{8}{9}N_D\pi\left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi}\gamma_H\gamma_D\hbar\right)^2\right]D_{trans}^{-3/2}\sqrt{\omega_H}, \quad (13)$$

under the assumption $(\omega_H \pm \omega_D) = \omega_H$.

III. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The compounds (glycine, glycine-d₅, l-aspartic acid, l-aspartic acid 2,3,3-d₃, l-aspartic acid-d₇, l-alanine, l-alanine-d₃, and l-alanine-d₄, glycerol) were purchased from Merck®. The mixtures listed in Table I were prepared.

¹H spin-lattice relaxation experiments were performed for the mixtures listed in Table I and pure glycerol as a reference in frequency range from 10 kHz to 10 MHz using a SMARtracer NMR relaxometer (Stelar s.r.l., Mede, Italy). Temperature was controlled with an accuracy of 0.5 K. The experiments started at 303 K, and then, the temperature was progressively decreased to 278 K. Pre-polarization was applied below 3.5 MHz. Each magnetization curve (magnetization vs time) includes 32 points.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

We have begun the analysis from glycerol in bulk as a reference system. Then, fully protonated systems, including two kinds of molecules, have been considered.

A. Glycerol as the reference system

The ¹H spin-lattice relaxation data for glycerol (glycerol-h₈) are shown in Fig. 1(a). The data have been reproduced in terms of Eq. (6) beginning with the lowest temperature of 278 K and using the four adjustable parameters: C_{intra}^{HH} , τ_c , D_{trans} , and d . The N_H number has been obtained from the relationship $N_H = \frac{nN_A\rho}{M}$, where $n = 8$ is the number of hydrogen atoms per molecule ($C_3H_8O_3$), N_A is Avogadro's number, $\rho = 1.26$ g/cm³ is the density of glycerol, and $M = 92.09$ g/mol is the molecular mass of glycerol; $N_H = 6.60 \times 10^{28}$ /m³. The decomposition of the relaxation data for 278 K into the inter-molecular and intra-molecular relaxation contributions, $R_1^{inter}(\omega_H)$ and $R_1^{intra}(\omega_H)$, respectively, is shown in Fig. 1(b). Already at the lowest temperature, $R_1^{intra}(\omega_H)$ shows only weak dependence on frequency in the covered frequency range. For the higher temperature, C_{intra}^{HH} and d have been set to the values obtained for 278 K and the fits have been performed in terms of two adjustable parameters: τ_c and D_{trans} . The diffusion coefficients, D_{trans} , have also been obtained from the low frequency slopes of $R_1(\omega_H)$ vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ [shown in the Appendix, Figs. 8(a) and 8(b)] using Eq. (12). The obtained values agree with each other and are in good agreement with those from Ref. 8; they are collected in Table II.

The correlation times, τ_c , are short. Consequently, the C_{intra}^{HH} value has been obtained from fitting the data at 278 K—in this case, the intra-molecular relaxation contribution still shows a dependence on the resonance frequency [Fig. 1(b)] and C_{intra}^{HH} and τ_c can be obtained separately as a result of the fit. For higher temperatures, the C_{intra}^{HH} value has been fixed to that obtained for 278 K. The same procedure has been applied to the mixtures discussed in Secs. IV B–IV D.

FIG. 1. (a) ¹H spin-lattice relaxation data for glycerol-h₈. Solid lines—fits in terms of Eq. (6); (b) decomposition of the overall relaxation rate, $R_1(\omega_H)$, into the inter-molecular, $R_1^{inter}(\omega_H)$, and intra-molecular, $R_1^{intra}(\omega_H)$, contributions (dashed and dashed-dotted lines, respectively).

TABLE II. Parameters characterizing dynamics of glycerol-h₈, $C_{intra}^{HH} = 4.39 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz}^2$, $d = 4.02 \text{ \AA}$ [Eq. (6)]. The term “(slope)” indicates the diffusion coefficients obtained from the low frequency slope of $R_1(\omega_H)$ vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ [Eq. (12)].

Temp. (K)	D_{trans} (m ² /s)	τ_c (s)	D_{trans} (m ² /s) (slope)
278	$(2.39 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$	$7.24 \times 10^{-9} \pm 6.67 \times 10^{-10}$	$2.41 \times 10^{-13} \pm 8.54 \times 10^{-15}$
283	$(5.20 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$	$3.74 \times 10^{-9} \pm 3.54 \times 10^{-11}$	$5.45 \times 10^{-13} \pm 1.20 \times 10^{-14}$
288	$6.54 \times 10^{-13} \pm 3.95 \times 10^{-15}$	$3.00 \times 10^{-9} \pm 3.16 \times 10^{-11}$	$6.83 \times 10^{-13} \pm 1.70 \times 10^{-14}$
293	$1.11 \times 10^{-12} \pm 4.53 \times 10^{-15}$	$1.90 \times 10^{-9} \pm 1.35 \times 10^{-11}$	$1.13 \times 10^{-12} \pm 1.70 \times 10^{-14}$
298	$1.75 \times 10^{-12} \pm 6.00 \times 10^{-15}$	$1.23 \times 10^{-9} \pm 7.71 \times 10^{-12}$	$1.75 \times 10^{-12} \pm 2.24 \times 10^{-14}$
303	$2.59 \times 10^{-12} \pm 1.04 \times 10^{-14}$	$8.85 \times 10^{-10} \pm 6.43 \times 10^{-12}$	$2.41 \times 10^{-12} \pm 3.08 \times 10^{-14}$

B. Fully protonated binary mixtures

Figure 2 shows ¹H spin-lattice relaxation data for fully protonated mixtures, including glycerol-h₈ as the first component (molecules 1) and fully protonated l-aspartic acid (l-aspartic acid-h₇), l-alanine (l-alanine-h₇), and glycine (glycine-h₅). Although this case should be described in terms of Eq. (8) (assuming the same values of the translation diffusion coefficient for both molecular fractions), it has turned out that the intra-molecular relaxation can be represented by a single term, so the description reduces to Eq. (6) with the effective parameters, C_{intra}^{HH} and τ_c . This simplification is caused by the fast rotational dynamics and, consequently, the weak frequency dependence on the intra-molecular relaxation contribution (at higher temperatures, the contribution becomes, in fact, frequency independent in the covered frequency range).

As pointed out in Sec. II, the description applies to the cases when the relaxation process is single-exponential. This has been carefully investigated. Examples of the magnetization curves (¹H magnetization vs time) are shown in the Appendix (Figs. 9–12) for glycerol and all three mixtures. The relaxation process is single exponential at all temperatures in the whole frequency range.

The fitting strategy has been the same as for the case of pure glycerol. The N_H numbers for the mixtures yield glycerol-h₈–l-aspartic acid-h₇: $N_H = 6.51 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$ ($N_{H,1} = 6.16 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$, $N_{H,2} = 0.35 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$, and $N_{H,2}/N_{H,1} = 0.057$); glycerol-h₈–l-alanine-h₇: $N_H = 6.61 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$ ($N_{H,1} = 5.97 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$, $N_{H,2} = 0.64 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$, and $N_{H,2}/N_{H,1} = 0.11$); and glycerol-h₈–glycine-h₅: $N_H = 6.59 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$ ($N_{H,1} = 4.71 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$, $N_{H,2} = 1.88 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$, and $N_{H,2}/N_{H,1} = 0.40$). For calculating the numbers, the following values have been used: $N_{H,1} = \frac{n_1 N_A \rho_1}{M_1}$, where $n_1 = 8$ is the number of hydrogen atoms per molecule ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$), N_A is Avogadro's number, $\rho_1 = 1.26 \text{ g/cm}^3$ is the density of glycerol, and $M_1 = 92.09 \text{ g/mol}$ is the molecular mass of glycerol (molecules 1). In the same way, $N_{H,2} = \frac{n_2 N_A \rho_2}{M_2}$, where n_2 is the number of hydrogen atoms per molecule of the second component (molecules 2), ρ_2 is the density of the second component, and M_2 is the molecular mass of the second component.

The amount of l-aspartic acid-h₇ in glycerol-h₈–l-aspartic acid-h₇ is low (about 6%, referring to the ratio between the numbers of hydrogen atoms per unit volume of the mixture, $N_{H,2}/N_{H,1}$); for the glycerol-h₈–l-alanine-h₇ mixture, the amount of l-alanine-h₇ is about 11%, while for glycerol-h₈–glycine-h₅, the amounts of both components are comparable (about 40% of glycine-h₅). The obtained parameters are collected in Table III. Table III also includes

the translation diffusion coefficients, D_{trans} , obtained from the low frequency linear dependencies of $R_1(\omega_H)$ on $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ [Eq. (12)]. The linear dependencies for the glycerol-h₈–glycine-h₅ mixture are shown in Fig. 13 (Appendix), while Figs. 14 and 15 for glycerol-h₈–l-aspartic acid-h₇ and glycerol-h₈–l-alanine-h₇, respectively, are also included into the Appendix.

The dipolar relaxation constants, C_{intra}^{HH} , and the values of the distance of the closest approach, d , should be treated as effective quantities accounting for the presence of both components—therefore, they somewhat differ from those for pure glycerol (actually, it has turned out that for the glycerol-h₈–l-alanine-h₇ mixture, the distance of the closest approach is the same as for pure glycerol). The translation diffusion coefficients, D_{trans} , as well as the rotational correlation times, τ_c (also being an effective quantity), for the mixtures and for pure glycerol are similar.

C. Binary mixtures with one protonated and one fully deuterated compounds

The translation diffusion coefficient, D_{trans} , and the correlation time, τ_c , determined in Sec. IV C stem from using Eq. (6) that provides a simplified description of the relaxation processes, not distinguishing between the molecular fractions.

To reveal the dynamics of glycerol in the presence of the second compound, glycerol-h₈–l-aspartic acid-d₇ and glycerol-h₈–glycine-d₅ mixtures have been considered, keeping the same proportion of the components as in the case of the fully protonated mixtures; glycerol-h₈–l-aspartic acid-d₇: $N_H = N_{H,1} = 6.16 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$, $N_D = 0.33 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$ and glycerol-h₈–glycine-d₅: $N_H = N_{H,1} = 4.71 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$, $N_D = 1.76 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$. The data for the first mixture glycerol-h₈–l-aspartic acid-d₇ are shown in Fig. 3. The relaxation process is single exponential—examples of the time evolution of the ¹H magnetization are shown in the Appendix (Fig. 16). Figures 3(b)–3(d) show a comparison of the relaxation data for glycerol-h₈–l-aspartic acid-d₇, glycerol-h₈–l-aspartic acid-h₇, and pure glycerol-h₈ at 278, 288, and 298 K, respectively.

The data have been analyzed in terms of Eq. (6), including only the ¹H–¹H relaxation contributions, as in this case, the N_D/N_H ratio is small (0.057). The dipolar relaxation constant has been set to that for glycerol-h₈. The obtained parameters, including the translation diffusion coefficient, D_{trans} , calculated from the linear dependencies $R_1(\omega_H)$ vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ in the low frequency range (Fig. 17, Appendix) in terms of Eq. (12) are collected in Table IV. We have also calculated

FIG. 2. ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for (a) glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- h_7 , (c) glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- h_7 , and (e) glycerol- h_8 -glycine- h_5 mixtures. Solid lines—fits in terms of Eq. (6). (b), (d), and (f) Corresponding decompositions of the overall relaxation rate, $R_1(\omega_H)$, into the inter-molecular, $R_1^{inter}(\omega_H)$, and intra-molecular, $R_1^{intra}(\omega_H)$, contributions (dashed and dashed-dotted lines, respectively).

the translation diffusion coefficient, D_{trans} , from Eq. (13) for comparison. As the differences do not exceed the uncertainties of the obtained values, we do not include the results in Table IV.

Figure 4 shows ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for the glycerol- h_8 -glycine- d_5 mixture. Figures 4(b)–4(d) show a comparison of the relaxation data for glycerol- h_8 -glycine- h_5 , glycerol- h_8 -glycine- d_5 , and glycerol- h_8 at 278, 288, and 298 K, respectively, in analogy to the previous case. The relaxation process is again single exponential—this is confirmed by the examples of the time evolution of the ^1H magnetization shown in the Appendix (Fig. 18). The

ratio between relaxation rates caused by ^1H - ^2H and ^1H - ^1H inter-molecular dipole-dipole interactions in the low frequency range is given as $\frac{16}{3} \left(\frac{\gamma_D}{\gamma_H} \right)^2 \frac{N_D}{N_H}$, which gives 0.055 for the glycerol- h_8 -glycine- d_5 mixture. As the ratio is small, Eq. (6) (not including the ^1H - ^2H relaxation contribution) has been used to interpret the relaxation data. Analogously to the case of glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_7 , the dipolar relaxation constant has been set to that for glycerol- h_8 : $C_{intra}^{HH} = 4.39 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz}^2$. The obtained parameters are collected in Table V, including the translation diffusion coefficient, D_{trans} , calculated from

TABLE III. Parameters characterizing dynamics of the glycerol-h₈-l-aspartic acid-h₇, glycerol-h₈-l-alanine-h₇, and glycerol-h₈-glycine-h₅ mixtures [Eq. (8) converged to Eq. (6)—a single intramolecular relaxation contribution]. The term “(slope)” indicates the diffusion coefficients obtained from the low frequency slope of $R_1(\omega_H)$ vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ [Eq. (12)].

Temp. (K)	D_{trans} (m ² /s)	τ_c (s)	D_{trans} (m ² /s) (slope)
Glycerol-h ₈ -l-aspartic acid-h ₇ , $C_{intra}^{HH} = 4.58 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz}^2$, $d = 3.94 \text{ \AA}$			
278	$(2.56 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$	$(6.72 \pm 0.10) \times 10^{-9}$	$(2.81 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-13}$
283	$(5.74 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$	$(3.27 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-9}$	$(6.03 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-13}$
288	$(7.38 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-13}$	$(2.62 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-9}$	$(7.62 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-13}$
293	$(1.33 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.54 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-9}$	$(1.30 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-12}$
298	$(1.90 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.12 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-9}$	$(1.91 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-12}$
303	$(2.73 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-12}$	$(7.96 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-10}$	$(2.72 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-12}$
Glycerol-h ₈ -l-alanine-h ₇ , $C_{intra}^{HH} = 4.31 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz}^2$, $d = 4.02 \text{ \AA}$			
278	$(2.76 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$	$(7.31 \pm 0.10) \times 10^{-9}$	$(2.86 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-13}$
283	$(5.81 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-13}$	$(3.56 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-9}$	$(6.00 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-13}$
288	$(7.77 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-13}$	$(2.83 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-9}$	$(7.92 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-13}$
293	$(1.38 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.73 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-9}$	$(1.31 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-12}$
298	$(1.98 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.21 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-9}$	$(2.00 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-12}$
303	$(2.81 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-12}$	$(8.86 \pm 0.10) \times 10^{-10}$	$(2.77 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-12}$
Glycerol-h ₈ -glycine-h ₅ , $C_{intra}^{HH} = 3.85 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz}^2$, $d = 3.85 \text{ \AA}$			
278	$(2.88 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$	$(7.63 \pm 0.20) \times 10^{-9}$	$(2.91 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-13}$
283	$(4.94 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-13}$	$(4.81 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-9}$	$(5.10 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-13}$
288	$(9.47 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-13}$	$(2.73 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-9}$	$(7.62 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-13}$
293	$(1.44 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.70 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-9}$	$(1.44 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-12}$
298	$(2.07 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.22 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-9}$	$(2.04 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-12}$
303	$(2.98 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-12}$	$(8.51 \pm 0.20) \times 10^{-10}$	$(2.95 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-12}$

the linear dependencies $R_1(\omega_H)$ vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ in the low frequency range (Fig. 19, Appendix), applying Eq. (12).

D. Binary mixtures with one protonated and one partially deuterated compounds

It is of interest to compare the relaxation features of binary mixtures with both non-deuterated components: one fully deuterated and one non-deuterated components and one non-deuterated and one partially deuterated components. Taking into account the differences in the relaxation rates between glycerol-h₈-l-aspartic acid-h₇ and glycerol-h₈-l-aspartic acid-d₇ seen in Fig. 3 (although the relative amount of the second component is low), glycerol-h₈-l-aspartic acid-d₃ has been chosen. The composition of the mixture is as follows: $N_H = 6.35 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$ ($N_{H,1} = 6.16 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$, $N_{H,2} = 0.19 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$) and $N_D = 0.14 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$. One should note that the composition of all the systems is the same in this sense that $(N_H + N_D)$ remains (almost) unchanged—the very small differences stem from somewhat different molecular masses of the protonated and deuterated compounds.

The relaxation data for glycerol-h₈-l-aspartic acid-d₃ are shown in Fig. 5(a), while Fig. 5(b) shows a comparison between the relaxation rates for glycerol-h₈-l-aspartic acid-h₇, glycerol-h₈-l-

aspartic acid-d₃, and glycerol-h₈-l-aspartic acid-d₇. In all cases, the relaxation processes are single exponential (Fig. 20, Appendix). As the relaxation rates for the first two mixtures differ only slightly, one can conclude that the differences between the data for glycerol-h₈-l-aspartic acid-h₇ and glycerol-h₈-l-aspartic acid-d₇ are associated rather with the contribution to the relaxation process of NH₂ than OH groups in l-aspartic acid.

Again, the data have been interpreted in terms of Eq. (6). The dipolar relaxation constant, C_{intra}^{HH} , and the distance of the closest approach, d , range between those for glycerol-h₈-l-aspartic acid-d₃ and glycerol-h₈-l-aspartic acid-d₇, as expected. The obtained parameters are collected in Table VI. The linear dependencies of $R_1(\omega_H)$ on $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ are shown in the Appendix, Fig. 21.

Following this line, relaxation properties of glycerol-h₈-l-alanine-d₃ and glycerol-h₈-l-alanine-d₄ mixtures have been investigated. The composition of the mixtures is as follows: glycerol-h₈-l-alanine-d₃: $N_H = 6.22 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$ ($N_{H,1} = 5.86 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$, $N_{H,2} = 0.35 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$), $N_D = 0.26 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$; glycerol-h₈-l-alanine-d₄: $N_H = 6.13 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$ ($N_{H,1} = 5.86 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$, $N_{H,2} = 0.26 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$), $N_D = 0.34 \times 10^{28}/\text{m}^3$. The relaxation data are shown in Figs. 6(a) and 6(b) for glycerol-h₈-l-alanine-d₃ and glycerol-h₈-l-alanine-d₄, respectively. Again, in all cases, the relaxation processes are single exponential (Figs. 22 and 23, Appendix). In

FIG. 3. (a) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_7 . Solid lines—fits in terms of Eq. (6). (b)–(d) Comparison of ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- h_7 , glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_7 , and glycerol- h_8 at 278, 288, and 298 K, respectively. Dashed lines—inter-molecular relaxation contributions, $R_1^{\text{inter}}(\omega_H)$; black for glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_7 .

TABLE IV. Parameters characterizing dynamics of the glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_7 mixture vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$; $C_{\text{intra}}^{\text{HH}} = 4.39 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz}^2$, $d = 3.75 \text{ \AA}$ [Eq. (6)]. The term “(slope)” indicates the diffusion coefficients obtained from the low frequency slope of $R_1(\omega_H)$ [Eq. (12)].

Temp. (K)	$D_{\text{trans}} (\text{m}^2/\text{s})$	$\tau_c (\text{s})$	$D_{\text{trans}} (\text{m}^2/\text{s})$ (slope)
278	$(3.40 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$	$(5.42 \pm 0.10) \times 10^{-9}$	$(3.41 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-13}$
283	$(6.86 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-13}$	$(2.80 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-9}$	$(6.85 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-13}$
288	$(8.62 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-13}$	$(2.26 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-9}$	$(8.61 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-13}$
293	$(1.53 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.34 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-9}$	$(1.50 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-12}$
298	$(2.20 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.00 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-9}$	$(2.22 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-12}$
303	$(3.02 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-12}$	$(7.26 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-10}$	$(3.05 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-12}$

Figs. 6(c) and 6(d), the relaxation data for glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- h_7 , glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_4 , glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_3 , and glycerol- h_8 at 278 and 298 K are compared.

The parameters obtained from Eqs. (6) and (12) are collected in Table VII. The dipolar relaxation constant, $C_{\text{intra}}^{\text{HH}}$, range between those for glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- h_7 and glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_7 , while the distance of the closest approach yields $d = 4.02 \text{ \AA}$, such as for glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- h_7 and glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_7 . The linear dependencies of $R_1(\omega_H)$ on $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ for the glycerol- h_8 -l-

alanine- d_3 and the glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_4 mixture are shown in Figs. 24 and 25 in the Appendix.

Figure 7 shows a comparison of the translation diffusion coefficients, D_{trans} , and the correlation times, τ_c , obtained for the discussed systems, respectively.

One can see in Fig. 7 linear dependences of logarithm of the diffusion coefficient on the reciprocal temperature, as expected for Arrhenius law. For clarity of Fig. 7, we do not show the fits. The activation energies vary between $(60.0 \pm 3.4) \text{ kJ/mol}$ for glycerol-

FIG. 4. (a) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for glycerol- h_8 -glycine- d_5 . Solid lines—fits in terms of Eq. (6). (b)–(d) Comparison of ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for glycerol- h_8 -glycine- h_5 , glycerol- h_8 -glycine- d_5 , and glycerol- h_8 at 278, 288, and 298 K, respectively. Dashed lines—inter-molecular relaxation contributions, $R_1^{\text{inter}}(\omega_H)$; black for glycerol- h_8 -glycine- d_5 .

h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_7 and (68.2 ± 3.4) kJ/mol for glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_4 ; for glycerol- h_8 , the activation energy yields (62.1 ± 4.2) kJ/mol, in agreement with Ref. 8.

V. DISCUSSION

In the first step, ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for glycerol- h_8 have been analyzed in terms of Eq. (6), including the inter-molecular and intra-molecular relaxation contributions. In addition, the translation diffusion coefficient of glycerol in bulk has been calculated

from the slope of the linear dependence of the spin-lattice relaxation rate on the square root of the resonance frequency [Eq. (12)]. Results for glycerol have already been reported;⁸ in this work, they serve as a reference for the further studies.

In the second step, we have analyzed ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for mixtures of glycerol- h_8 and fully protonated l-aspartic acid (l-aspartic acid- h_7), l-alanine (l-alanine- h_7), and glycine (glycine- h_5). For the first two mixtures (glycerol and l-aspartic acid; glycerol and l-alanine), the contribution of ^1H from the second component is low—the $N_{\text{H},2}/N_{\text{H},1}$ ratio is of about 6% and 11%, respectively;

TABLE V. Parameters characterizing dynamics of the glycerol- h_8 -glycine- d_5 mixture, $C_{\text{intra}}^{\text{HH}} = 4.39 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz}^2$, $d = 3.49 \text{ \AA}$ [Eq. (6)]. The term “(slope)” indicates the diffusion coefficients obtained from the low frequency slope of $R_1(\omega_H)$ vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ [Eq. (12)].

Temp. (K)	D_{trans} (m^2/s)	τ_c (s)	D_{trans} (m^2/s) (slope)
278	$(3.04 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$	$(5.52 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-9}$	$(3.17 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-13}$
283	$(5.07 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-13}$	$(3.50 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-9}$	$(5.47 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-13}$
288	$(8.08 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-13}$	$(2.23 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-9}$	$(8.35 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$
293	$(1.39 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.39 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-9}$	$(1.48 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-12}$
298	$(2.10 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-12}$	$(9.24 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-10}$	$(2.19 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-12}$
303	$(2.76 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-12}$	$(7.46 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-10}$	$(2.90 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-12}$

FIG. 5. (a) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_3 . Solid lines—fits in terms of Eq. (6). (b)–(d) Comparison of ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- h_7 , glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_3 , and glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_7 and glycerol- h_8 at 278, 288, and 298 K. Dashed and dashed-dotted lines—intermolecular and intra-molecular relaxation contributions, $R_1^{\text{inter}}(\omega_H)$ and $R_1^{\text{intra}}(\omega_H)$, respectively, for glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_3 at 278, 288, and 298 K.

TABLE VI. Parameters characterizing dynamics of the glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_3 mixture, $C_{\text{intra}}^{\text{HH}} = 4.43 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz}^2$, $d = 3.97 \text{ \AA}$ [Eq. (10) converged to Eq. (6)]. The term “(slope)” indicates the diffusion coefficients obtained from the low frequency slope of $R_1(\omega_H)$ vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ [Eq. (12)].

Temp. (K)	$D_{\text{trans}} (\text{m}^2/\text{s})$	$\tau_c (\text{s})$	$D_{\text{trans}} (\text{m}^2/\text{s})$ (slope)
278	$(2.67 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-13}$	$(6.88 \pm 0.10) \times 10^{-9}$	$(2.68 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-13}$
283	$(4.69 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-13}$	$(4.17 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-9}$	$(4.58 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-13}$
288	$(7.50 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-13}$	$(2.69 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-9}$	$(6.96 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-13}$
293	$(1.32 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.63 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-9}$	$(1.31 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-12}$
298	$(1.95 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.13 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-9}$	$(1.86 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-12}$
303	$(2.67 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-12}$	$(8.36 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-10}$	$(2.53 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-12}$

for the glycerol and glycine mixture, the ratio is much higher, about 40%. In principle, the results should be analyzed in terms of Eq. (12), including several relaxation contributions and, consequently, several unknown parameters. Instead of that, we have attempted to reproduce the data in terms of Eq. (6), including single inter-molecular and intra-molecular relaxation contributions and setting $N_H = H_{H,1} + H_{H,2}$. The attempt has turned out to be successful with the effective translation diffusion coefficients being close to that of glycerol in bulk. The same outcome has been obtained from Eq. (12)—one should notice that Eq. (12) always leads to a single diffusion coefficient (a sum of two linear dependences forms a

linear dependence). The distance of the closest approach has been somewhat affected by the presence of the second component—it reflects now the effective distance. Analogously, the somewhat different dipolar relaxation constant, $C_{\text{intra}}^{\text{HH}}$, accounts for the presence of both kinds of molecules. The correlation time, τ_c , also represents an effective value, not differing significantly from that for glycerol in bulk. One can suppose that Eq. (6) has turned out to be sufficient because of the fast rotational dynamics (short τ_c). A stronger frequency dependence of the intra-molecular relaxation contribution would likely lead to the need of using Eq. (8) with two intra-molecular relaxation contributions. One should keep this

FIG. 6. (a) and (b) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_3 and glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_4 . Solid lines—fits in terms of Eq. (6). (c) and (d) Comparison of ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- h_7 , glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_4 , glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_3 , and glycerol- h_8 at 278 and 298 K. Dashed and dashed-dotted lines—inter-molecular and intra-molecular relaxation contributions, respectively, for glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_4 (black) and glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_3 (wine).

TABLE VII. Parameters characterizing dynamics of the glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_3 and glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_4 mixtures [Eq. (6)]. The term “(slope)” indicates the diffusion coefficients obtained from the low frequency slope of $R_1(\omega_H)$ vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ [Eq. (12)].

Temp. (K)	D_{trans} (m^2/s)	τ_c (s)	D_{trans} (m^2/s) (slope)
Glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_3 , $C_{\text{intra}}^{\text{HH}} = 4.01 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz}^2$, $d = 4.02 \text{ \AA}$			
278	$(3.53 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$	$(6.94 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-9}$	$(3.67 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-13}$
283	$(7.54 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-13}$	$(3.41 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-9}$	$(8.06 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-13}$
288	$(9.60 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-13}$	$(2.67 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-9}$	$(9.17 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$
293	$(1.76 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.57 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-9}$	$(1.82 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-12}$
298	$(2.46 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.18 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-9}$	$(2.48 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-12}$
303	$(3.52 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-12}$	$(8.73 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-10}$	$(3.52 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-12}$
Glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_4 , $C_{\text{intra}}^{\text{HH}} = 4.18 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz}^2$, $d = 4.02 \text{ \AA}$			
278	$(2.50 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$	$(8.33 \pm 0.10) \times 10^{-9}$	$(2.75 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-13}$
283	$(5.29 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-13}$	$(3.58 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-9}$	$(5.59 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-13}$
288	$(6.80 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-13}$	$(3.19 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-9}$	$(7.33 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-13}$
293	$(1.28 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.89 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-9}$	$(1.37 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-12}$
298	$(2.22 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.18 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-9}$	$(2.32 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-12}$
303	$(3.14 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{-12}$	$(8.57 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-10}$	$(3.13 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-12}$

FIG. 7. (a) Translation diffusion coefficients and (b) correlation times τ_c for glycerol-l-aspartic acid, glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine, and glycerol- h_8 -glycine mixtures.

possibility in mind before resorting to non-Lorentzian forms of spectral densities (such as the Cole-Davidson spectral density) to reproduce these kinds of data; such semi-phenomenological models have a limited meaning. The data could also be interpreted involving three inter-molecular relaxation contributions [Eq. (7)]. One could fix $d_{1,1}$ and $D_{trans,1}$ to the values obtained for glycerol in bulk and treat $d_{2,2}$, $d_{1,2}$, and $D_{trans,2}$ as adjustable parameters—such analysis would, however, be ambiguous.

Following this line, in the third step, the relaxation processes in the mixtures: glycerol- h_8 and l-aspartic acid- d_7 and glycerol- h_8 and glycine- d_5 (the second component being fully deuterated). As already pointed out, the parameters obtained for the case when both components are protonated represent the effective (averaged) dynamics; however, one should not expect that the dynamics of both the components is considerably different (especially as the parameters are close to that for glycerol in bulk). Nevertheless, the deuteration enables verification of this statement. In the case of glycerol- h_8 and l-aspartic acid- d_7 , the low ratio N_D/N_H brings one to Eqs. (6) and (12) instead of Eqs. (10) and (13). The diffusion coefficients obtained from Eq. (12) and from the fit [Eq. (6)] are in good agreement. Performing the fit in terms of Eq. (6), the distance of the closest approach, d , has been treated as an adjustable parameter—the obtained values are slightly smaller than for glycerol in bulk. The correlation time τ_c is close to that for bulk glycerol (C_{intra}^{HH} has been fixed to that for bulk glycerol). Although the N_D/N_H ratio for the glycerol- h_8 and glycine- d_5 is much higher, the relative low gyromagnetic factor of 2H leads to a small difference (within the uncertainty range) between the diffusion coefficients of glycerol obtained from Eqs. (12) and (13). However, when it comes to the full analysis of the data, one should be aware that the 1H - 2H inter-molecular contribution might not be negligible as it also depends on the $d_{1,2}$ value that might be smaller than $d_{1,1}$ (for $d_{1,1} = d_{1,2}$, the 1H - 2H relaxation contribution can be omitted). Agreement between the diffusion coefficients obtained from Eq. (12) and from Eq. (6) shows that using Eq. (6) is sufficient. Eventually, in the last step, the relaxation data for the glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_3 and glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_3 and glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_4 mixtures have been analyzed [using Eqs. (6) and (12)]. The challenge lies in obtaining a consistent interpretation with respect to the fully protonated mixtures and the mixtures in which the second component is fully deuterated, and this goal has been achieved.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The presented theoretical model of relaxation processes in binary molecular systems, accounting for all relevant inter-molecular and intra-molecular relaxation pathways (including 1H - 1H and 1H - 2H dipole-dipole interactions), provides a robust framework for revealing dynamical properties of binary liquids on the basis of NMR relaxometry data. The model has been thoroughly tested against several combinations of molecules of different levels of deuteration, leading to consistent results. Although interpreting the data for the systems used as examples, we have not exploited the description of relaxation processes involving several relaxation pathways [such as Eq. (7) or Eq. (11)]; the need of using the extended models should be carefully considered depending on the composition of the specific binary system. For the binary mixtures considered in this work, it has been demonstrated that both components undergo translational and rotational dynamics that is similar to that of glycerol in bulk.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Adriane Consuelo Leal Aucaise: Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **Elzbieta Masiewicz:** Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal). **Karol Kolodziejcki:** Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal). **Danuta Kruk:** Conceptualization (lead); Methodology (lead); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (lead).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10560015>.

APPENDIX: ^1H MAGNETIZATION CURVES AND LOW FREQUENCY LINEAR DEPENDENCIES OF SPIN-LATTICE RELAXATION RATES

FIG. 8. (a) and (b) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data, $R_1(\omega_H)$, vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ for glycerol. Solid lines—linear dependences in the range of $\omega_H T_{\text{trans}} < 1$.

FIG. 9. (a) and (b) Normalized ^1H time evolution of magnetization for glycerol- h_8 at selected resonance frequencies in the temperatures 303 and 278 K, respectively. The top and right axis corresponds to frequencies 335 and 10 kHz, while bottom and left axis for 10 and 4.95 MHz. Solid lines—single exponential fits.

FIG. 10. (a) and (b) Normalized ^1H time evolution of magnetization for the glycerol- h_8 /l-aspartic acid- h_7 binary mixture at selected resonance frequencies in the temperatures 303 and 278 K, respectively. Top and right axis corresponds to frequencies 335 and 10 kHz, while bottom and left axis for 10 and 4.95 MHz. Solid lines—single exponential fits.

FIG. 11. (a) and (b) Normalized ^1H time evolution of magnetization for the glycerol- h_8 /l-alanine- h_7 binary mixture at selected resonance frequencies in the temperatures 303 and 278 K, respectively. Top and right axis corresponds to frequencies 335 and 10 kHz, while bottom and left axis for 10 and 4.95 MHz. Solid lines—single exponential fits.

FIG. 12. (a) and (b) Normalized ^1H time evolution of magnetization for the glycerol- h_8 /glycine- h_5 binary mixture at selected resonance frequencies in the temperatures 303 and 278 K, respectively. Top and right axis corresponds to frequencies 335 and 10 kHz, while bottom and left axis for 10 and 4.95 MHz. Solid lines—single exponential fits.

FIG. 13. (a) and (b) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data, $R_1(\omega_H)$, vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ for the glycerol- h_8 -glycine- h_5 mixture. Solid lines—linear dependences in the range of $\omega_H\tau_{trans} < 1$.

FIG. 14. (a) and (b) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data, $R_1(\omega_H)$, vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ for the glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- h_7 mixture. Solid lines—linear dependences in the range of $\omega_H \tau_{\text{trans}} < 1$.

FIG. 15. (a) and (b) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data, $R_1(\omega_H)$, vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ for the glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- h_7 mixture. Solid lines—linear dependences in the range of $\omega_H \tau_{\text{trans}} < 1$.

FIG. 16. (a) and (b) Normalized ^1H time evolution of magnetization for the glycerol- h_8 /l-aspartic acid- d_7 binary mixture at selected resonance frequencies in the temperatures 303 and 278 K, respectively. The top and right axis corresponds to frequencies 335 and 10 kHz, while bottom and left axis for 10 and 4.95 MHz. Solid lines—single exponential fits.

FIG. 17. (a) and (b) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data, $R_1(\omega_H)$, vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ for the glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_7 mixture. Solid lines—linear dependences in the range of $\omega_H \tau_{\text{trans}} < 1$.

FIG. 18. (a) and (b) Normalized ^1H time evolution of magnetization for the glycerol- h_8 /glycine- d_5 binary mixture at selected resonance frequencies in the temperatures 303 and 278 K, respectively. The top and right axis corresponds to frequencies 335 and 10 kHz, while bottom and left axis for 10 and 4.95 MHz. Solid lines—single exponential fits.

FIG. 19. (a) and (b) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data, $R_1(\omega_H)$, vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ for the glycerol- h_8 -glycine- d_5 mixture. Solid lines—linear dependences in the range of $\omega_H \tau_{\text{trans}} < 1$.

FIG. 20. (a) and (b) Normalized ^1H time evolution of magnetization for the glycerol- h_8 /l-aspartic acid- d_3 binary mixture at selected resonance frequencies in the temperatures 303 and 278 K, respectively. The top and right axis corresponds to frequencies 335 and 10 kHz, while bottom and left axis for 10 and 4.95 MHz. Solid lines—single exponential fits.

FIG. 21. (a) and (b) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data, $R_1(\omega_H)$, vs. $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ for the glycerol- h_8 -l-aspartic acid- d_3 mixture. Solid lines—linear dependences in the range of $\omega_H \tau_{\text{trans}} < 1$.

FIG. 22. (a) and (b) Normalized ^1H time evolution of magnetization for the glycerol- h_8 /l-alanine- d_3 binary mixture at selected resonance frequencies in the temperatures 303 and 278 K, respectively. The top and right axis corresponds to frequencies 335 and 10 kHz, while bottom and left axis for 10 and 4.95 MHz. Solid lines—single exponential fits.

FIG. 23. (a) and (b) Normalized ^1H time evolution of magnetization for the glycerol- h_8 /l-alanine- d_4 binary mixture at selected resonance frequencies in the temperatures 303 and 278 K, respectively. The top and right axis corresponds to frequencies 335 and 10 kHz, while bottom and left axis for 10 and 4.95 MHz. Solid lines—single exponential fits.

FIG. 24. (a) and (b) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data, $R_1(\omega_H)$, vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ for the glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_3 mixture. Solid lines—linear dependences in the range of $\omega_H\tau_{trans} < 1$.

FIG. 25. (a) and (b) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data, $R_1(\omega_H)$, vs $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ for the glycerol- h_8 -l-alanine- d_4 mixture. Solid lines—linear dependences in the range of $\omega_H\tau_{trans} < 1$.

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REFERENCES

- ¹A. Abragam, *Principles of Nuclear Magnetism*, Reprinted (Oxford Science Publications, Cidade Tal, 1994).
- ²C. P. Slichter, *Principles of Magnetic Resonance*, 3rd ed. (Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, New York, 1992).
- ³D. Kruk, *Understanding Spin Dynamics* (Pan Stanford Publishing, Singapore, 2016).
- ⁴J. Kowalewski and L. Maler, *Nuclear Spin Relaxation in Liquids: Theory, Experiments, and Applications*, 2nd ed. (CRC Press; Taylor & Francis Group, Boca Raton, FL, 2019).
- ⁵Y. Ayant, E. Belorizky, J. Aluzon, and J. Gallice, "Calcul des densités spectrales résultant d'un mouvement aléatoire de translation en relaxation par interaction dipolaire magnétique dans les liquides," *J. Phys. France* **36**, 991–1004 (1975).
- ⁶L. P. Hwang and J. H. Freed, "Dynamic effects of pair correlation functions on spin relaxation by translational diffusion in liquids," *J. Chem. Phys.* **63**, 4017–4025 (1975).
- ⁷J. Korb, "Multiscale nuclear magnetic relaxation dispersion of complex liquids in bulk and confinement," *Prog. Nucl. Magn. Reson. Spectrosc.* **104**, 12–55 (2018).
- ⁸D. Kruk, R. Meier, and E. A. Rössler, "Translational and rotational diffusion of glycerol by means of field cycling ¹H NMR relaxometry," *J. Phys. Chem. B* **115**, 951–957 (2011).
- ⁹R. Meier, D. Kruk, J. Gmeiner, and E. A. Rössler, "Intermolecular relaxation in glycerol as revealed by field cycling ¹H NMR relaxometry dilution experiments," *J. Chem. Phys.* **136**, 034508 (2012).
- ¹⁰R. Meier, D. Kruk, A. Bourdick, E. Schneider, and E. A. Rössler, "Inter- and intramolecular relaxation in molecular liquids by field cycling ¹H NMR relaxometry," *Appl. Magn. Reson.* **44**, 153–168 (2013).
- ¹¹D. Kruk, P. Rochowski, E. Masiewicz, S. Wilczynski, M. Wojciechowski, L. M. Broche, and D. J. Lurie, "Mechanism of water dynamics in hyaluronic dermal fillers revealed by nuclear magnetic resonance relaxometry," *ChemPhysChem* **20**, 2816–2822 (2019).
- ¹²P. H. Fries, "Dipolar nuclear spin relaxation in liquids and plane fluids undergoing chemical reactions," *Mol. Phys.* **48**, 503–526 (2006).
- ¹³D. S. Grebenkov, Y. A. Goddard, G. Diakova, J.-P. Korb, and R. G. Bryant, "Dimensionality of diffusive exploration at the protein interface in solution," *J. Phys. Chem. B* **113**, 13347–13356 (2009).
- ¹⁴C. Luchinat, G. Parigi, and E. Ravera, "Water and protein dynamics in sedimented systems: A relaxometric investigation," *ChemPhysChem* **14**, 3156–3161 (2013).
- ¹⁵D. Kruk, M. Wojciechowski, M. Florek-Wojciechowska, and R. K. Singh, "Dynamics of ionic liquids in confinement by means of NMR relaxometry—EMIM-FSI in a silica matrix as an example," *Materials* **13**(19), 4351–4367 (2020).
- ¹⁶E. Belorizky, P. H. Fries, A. Guillermo, and O. Poncelet, "Almost ideal 1D water diffusion in imogolite nanotubes evidenced by NMR relaxometry," *ChemPhysChem* **11**, 2021–2026 (2010).
- ¹⁷R. Kimmich and N. Fatkullin, "Polymer chain dynamics and NMR," *Adv. Polym. Sci.* **170**, 1–113 (2004).
- ¹⁸R. Kimmich and N. Fatkullin, "Self-diffusion studies by intra- and inter-molecular spin-lattice relaxometry using field-cycling: Liquids, plastic crystals, porous media, and polymer segments," *Prog. Nucl. Magn. Reson. Spectrosc.* **101**, 18–50 (2017).
- ¹⁹D. Kruk, R. Meier, and E. A. Rössler, "Nuclear magnetic resonance relaxometry as a method of measuring translational diffusion coefficients in liquids," *Phys. Rev. E* **85**, 020201 (2012).
- ²⁰D. Kruk, R. Meier, A. Rachocki, A. Korpala, R. K. Singh, and E. A. Rössler, "Determining diffusion coefficients of ionic liquids by means of field cycling nuclear magnetic resonance relaxometry," *J. Chem. Phys.* **140**(24), 244509 (2014).
- ²¹D. Kruk, E. Masiewicz, S. Lotarska, R. Markiewicz, and S. Jurga, "Relationship between translational and rotational dynamics of alkyltriethylammonium-based ionic liquids," *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **23**, 1688 (2022).
- ²²G. Parigi, E. Ravera, M. Fragai, and C. Luchinat, "Unveiling protein dynamics in solution with field-cycling NMR relaxometry," *Prog. Nucl. Magn. Reson. Spectrosc.* **124–125**, 85–98 (2021).
- ²³T. Janc, J.-P. Korb, M. Luksic, V. Vlachy, R. G. Bryant, G. Meriguet, N. Malikova, and A.-L. Rollet, "Multiscale water dynamics on protein surfaces: Protein-specific response to surface ions," *J. Phys. Chem. B* **125**, 8673–8681 (2021).
- ²⁴M. Wencka, T. Apih, R. C. Korošec, J. Jencyk, M. Jarek, K. Szutkowski, S. Jurga, and J. Dolinšek, "Molecular dynamics of 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium triflate ionic liquid studied by ¹H and ¹⁹F nuclear magnetic resonances," *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **19**, 15368–15376 (2017).
- ²⁵A. O. Seyedlar, S. Stapf, and C. Mattea, "Dynamics of the ionic liquid 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulphonyl)imide studied by nuclear magnetic resonance dispersion and diffusion," *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **17**, 1653–1659 (2014).
- ²⁶K. Pilar, A. Rua, S. N. Suarez, C. Mallia, S. Lai, J. R. P. Jayakody, J. L. Hatcher, J. F. Wishart, and S. Greenbaum, "Investigation of dynamics in BMIM TFSA ionic liquid through variable temperature and pressure NMR relaxometry and diffusometry," *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **164**, 5189–5196 (2017).
- ²⁷D. Kruk, E. Masiewicz, K. Kolodziejcki, R. Markiewicz, and S. Jurga, "Relative cation-anion diffusion in alkyltriethylammonium-based ionic liquids," *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **23**(11), 5994 (2022).
- ²⁸A. G. Redfield, *Encyclopedia of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance, Relaxation Theory: Density Matrix Formulation* (Wiley, Chichester, 1996), pp. 4085–4092.
- ²⁹M. Goldman, "Formal theory of spin-lattice relaxation," *J. Magn. Reson.* **149**, 160–187 (2001).
- ³⁰D. Kruk and O. Lips, "Field-dependent nuclear relaxation of spins 1/2 induced by dipole-dipole couplings to quadrupole spins: LaF₃ crystals as an example," *J. Magn. Reson.* **179**(2), 250–262 (2006).